

Abstract: Some brief ideas about physical, fundamental quanta are presented. The quantum is proposed to be a massless, inert, rigid sphere. Quanta make up all particles. Space must be filled with quanta, but the degree to which space is filled with quanta is not proposed here. Because quanta are massless and perfectly rigid, simple changes of motion due to collisions will be instantaneous, if not immediately impeded by collisions with other moving quanta. Thus, instantaneous action at a distance can occur across the diameter of a quantum.

Consider two massless, rigid spheres **A** and **B** colliding, with **A** initially moving:

If **B** is at rest, it will be brought to the speed of **A** instantaneously.

If **B** is moving slower than **A** and in the same direction as **A**, **B** will be brought to the speed of **A** instantaneously.

If **B** is moving at the same speed as **A** and in the opposite direction to **A**, both **A** and **B** will be stopped instantaneously.

If **B** is moving slower than **A** and in the opposite direction to **A**, **A** and **B** will be brought to the difference of their two speeds instantaneously and moving in the initial direction of **A**.

The last case follows from the previous cases. Given speeds v_A and v_B , their final speed will be $v_A - v_B$.

Collisions of massless quanta moving in opposite directions might conceivably be the basis of inertial effects. Consistent inertial effects would only be possible with an absolute rest frame of reference. It is shown in another paper that an absolute rest frame of reference is compatible with a reinterpretation of Special Relativity. Modern data suggest that the rest frame of the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation is the absolute rest frame of the Universe.

Particles of matter last almost indefinitely, so their constituent quanta must be largely impervious to slowing or stopping. Photons can be absorbed by matter, so their constituent quanta moving at light speed can be stopped, at least in translation. The paper **Electron Geometry** shows an electron comprised of a quantum traversing a toroidal orbit.